

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/384356445>

Reusability of the Potassium Iodide Solution for O₃ Determination Without Degradation

Conference Paper · September 2024

CITATIONS

0

READS

21

2 authors:

[Mirkan Emir Sancak](#)

Gebze Technical University

3 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

[ulker diler keris sen](#)

Gebze Technical University

10 PUBLICATIONS 260 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

REUSABILITY OF THE POTASSIUM IODIDE SOLUTION FOR O₃ DETERMINATION WITHOUT DEGRADATION

Mirkan Emir SANCAK

Gebze Technical University, Environmental Engineering

ORCID: 0000-0001-7237-2047

Ülker Diler KERİŞ-ŞEN

Gebze Technical University, Earth and Marine Sciences Institute

ORCID: 0000-0002-8354-1640

ABSTRACT

Potassium iodide (KI) is one of the critical reagent used in ozone determination. The measurement of ozone (O₃) concentration in water sample is based on the oxidation of iodide (I⁻) in KI by O₃, converting it to iodine (I₂). In this study, the feasibility of using KI for O₃ concentration measurement was evaluated, along with testing how many times KI can be used while maintaining consistent results. The O₃ concentration was calculated by re-titrating the same KI solution with 0.1N sodium thiosulphate (Na₂S₂O₃), without replacing the KI solution, and the regenerated KI solution was reused in subsequent experiments. In the experiments, two different ozone dosages were tested with non-thermal plasma: an average of 0.8 mg O₃/min was maintained for 17 cycles, each lasting 60 minutes, and an average of 0.2 mg O₃/min was maintained for another 17 cycles of 60 minutes each, with nearly the same amount of ozone being measured in both cases that was shown in Figure 1.

The result indicate that the same KI solution can be used up to 34 cycles without a significant change in O₃ concentration. On going to reaction with the same KI solution, the colour of the KI solution did not change.

This study was conducted to explore the potential of reusing a chemical reagent multiple times and contributes significantly to the literature by aiming to reduce environmental harm in various perspective. On the other hand, we have an evidence that the KI solution can be used for O₃ measurement more than a thousand minutes without altering the result.

Figure 1. O₃ concentration (mg/min) across multiple cycles during high and low ozone generation

This study was funded by TUBITAK (The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye) 122Y089 project.

Keywords: Reusable Chemicals; Ozone Determination; Environmental Sustainability